

To Investigate Behavioral Changes Across Different Cultures At University Level

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 08 , 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Behavioral Variations, Pakistani & Chinese Students, Culture</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6011613</p>	<p><i>This study examines the behavioral changes across different cultures at university level. Descriptive design was used by survey method. BS and MS Female students of Education department of International Islamic University were considered as population of this study. 785 samples were calculated through Epi Tool- a free web-based calculator. Self-developed questionnaire was used in this study. It consisted of 35 items. Descriptive (Mean & Percentage) and inferential statistics (t-test and ANOVA test) were used to analyzed data. It was found that Female students were neutral about their behavioral variations across different culture like stereotypical, migration, social attitude and behavior, coping strategy and performance and adaptation at university level. Nationality and level of Education had no significant effect over the students' opinions about behavioral variations across different culture at university level.</i></p>

Introduction

Behavior is influenced by different levels of culture like from individual to group level and all human beings belong to specific culture. Culture in returns provides social standards and expectations to participate in society (Fatima, 2019). Behaviors not only include observer able changes, it also includes our thinking patterns, perception and cognition (Ramburuth, 2000). All these mental processes can have impact on our learnt behavior because culture varies from individual to individual, region to region, and country to country (Sandaker, 2009). Cultural diversity involves the difference in race, ethnicity, and language and sociality is the characteristic of behavior that makes our culture. It fosters the process of socialization which causes transmission of culture and behavioral changes. Basically, culture is the combination of both human learning capability and social behavior (McInerney& King, 2012). In this regard culture includes patterns of learnt behavior in the form of values, customs and beliefs. Culture refers to set of ideas, beliefs, values, customs, traditions, habits, language, religion and social norms and behaviors of particular society (Lund & Rundmo, 2009).

Researchers have experienced the process of acculturation through migration from Swabi (KPK) to Islamabad (Punjab). Though there are not huge intercultural differences as these are provinces of Pakistan but they have faced cultural changes mostly due to variations in language, cultural traditions, academic and educational system, dresses, living standards and life styles. As the culture distance was not huge so acculturation takes place with little complicity and it did not lead to acculturative stress. Punjab is a dominant culture (society of settlement) and Pathan is a non-dominant culture (society of origin) (Fatima & Ali, 2019). Factors that help them in this process include their academic institution, excessive social interaction (first hand contact) with people of Islamabad. I have followed the integration strategy as they continued with both cultures to create balance and dominant group followed multiculturalism strategy as they allowed us to participate in their culture. The new society is multicultural as it has many dialects and people from different areas. They settled in Islamabad and it is totally different from Pashtun culture in terms of their mindsets and beliefs in terms of values, traditions and mostly narrow and traditional thoughts and living patterns such as join family system in swabi. Here they have seen that people mean their own business and everyone has its own personal space .no one is concerned about others like where the other person is going and what he is doing. Secondly, educational and academic variables make me learn this culture so fast through teachers, peer group and social interaction with different people in daily life. Much of the knowledge I get from my academic books and curriculum. It has helped me in speaking Urdu fluently and changed my accent. In this migration, pull factors were stronger than push factors. Behavioral changes occurred such as personality dimension e.g., way of speaking in different context, Urdu language, then the English medium school, cognitive beliefs are much broaden and reaction /coping strategies through experiencing little tough time in the beginning and interacting with others. Minimum cultural shredding and moderate to substantial culture learning occurs. There was big clash or conflict between these two cultures though it took time to learn new one. Social support was given by their teachers, friends, family, and neighbors. By keeping in view all these circumstances, this study examines the behavioral changes

across different cultures at university level and what relationship exists between human behavior and culture. Moreover, this study measures the degree of behavioral variations among university students representing different cultures captivating demographics features of selected sample regarding cultural impact on behavior. This study is intended to:

1. To examine the student's behavior belonging to different cultures providing in same social context at university level.
2. To find out the effect of demographic factors (qualification, age and nationality) regarding behavioral changes across different cultures at university level.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework is based on the Berry (2003)'s work which explains acculturation process and to examine the factors that has impact on individual's process of adaptation. His model's left side is based on group level while individual or psychological phenomena are on right side. At the top are the features which indicate those processes that exist prior to acculturation while those on the bottom indicate those that arise during the process of acculturation itself. the mid of the model shows main group- and psychological level acculturation phenomena flows from left to right direction in the beginning when cultural groups interact. this has impact on students/individuals who are experiencing the acculturation process. As a result, it proceeds to an individual's adaptation which can be occurred as either psychological or sociocultural. Psychological adaptation includes affective outcomes those linked to the individual's well-being, self-esteem, and satisfaction of his life. Sociocultural adaptation includes outcomes of behavior which relate to the ability to interact /communicate productively/constructively with students/people from the host/local culture and the tendency to cope with daily life problems and issues specifically in space/areas of life, family, and work. This framework represents the main variables that should be tackled during acculturation process.

Figure 1: *Theoretical Framework of behavioral variations across cultures*

The moderating factors before acculturation process such as gender (male/female), age, qualification, status, religion and what were the motivating factors such as pull/push factors. The moderating factors after the acculturation process includes social attitudes of host culture and social support given to individuals by host culture, and what acculturative and coping strategies are used but students to solve problems and to deal with acculturative stress. The process become complex if the student cannot use an appropriate strategy to overcome the problems this can cause result anxiety and depression if the student successes in using the appropriate acculturative strategies to overcome acculturative stress, he/she will produce adaptations (either psychological or sociocultural).

Relationship between Culture and Behavior

People from different countries and different regions often do things very differently. One way to explain the difference and variation among them is called culture (Treven, Mulej& Lynn, 2008). The major differences in how people from different cultures communicate with each other are language usage, verbal style, and non-verbal communication. A primary outcome examined within the culture learning approach is socio-cultural adaptation, which refers to behavioral outcomes of the acculturation process (Smaldino, Lukaszewski, Rueden&Gurven, 2019). Cross-cultural differences may implement an important influence on individualism/collectivism in classroom/school setting. Collectivism as its opposite pertains to societies in which people from birth to onwards are integrated into strong, cohesive in-groups which continue to protect them in exchange for unquestioning loyalty (Schwartz & Zamboanga, 2008). In the broadest sense, students from individualist cultures may want to stand out in class, to ask questions, give answers, and engage in debate. However, students from collectivist cultures are more strongly motivated to fit in and are less likely to be vocal in class. They are less willing to draw attention to themselves (Rana, Fatima & Sultan, 2021). Moreover,

“collectivism is also strongly related to power distance, which refers to the degree to which societies emphasize hierarchy and respect for authority” (Probstl-Haider & Mostegl, 2019). “Individuals /students from high power distance cultures may be less likely to engage in questions and debates. Questioning the teacher may be seen by these students as inappropriate and may even result in a loss of face. These differences in cultural values may result in motivational decline for the students especially when the students perceive a certain degree of incongruence in their learning” (McInerney & King, 2012).

2.2 Factors Involved in Determining Behavior of Students

Empirical studies have provided support for explaining the difficulties of international students that were produced due to intercultural difference like international students were often critical of informality in the classroom, perceived lack of respect for professors, and insufficient focus in classroom interactions revealed by the United States research with Asian students. They were also occasionally disparaging of their American peers’ perceived egotism. “Stated by Japanese students, American students seem to want to show off their knowledge and intelligence in class and are often overconfident and egotistical; discussions seem to be like competition” (Kumar, Anjum & Sinha, 2011). These differences pertained to classroom participation and teacher student relationships. More specifically, students wanted more error correction, believed more strongly in the acceptance of teacher authority, and had a stronger tendency to agree with the teacher. On the other hand, teachers expected their students to have an internal locus of academic control (McInerney & King, 2012). “Coping with the cross-cultural transition was seen as an instance (or instances) of readjusting one’s self in relation to significant life changes. Individuals appraise novel cultural situations in different ways which in turn affects subsequent psychological outcomes. In most cases, this novelty was interpreted as stressful and increased psychological adjustment problems” (Koneru, Mamani, Flynn & Betancourt, 2007). International students can also find lectures hard to understand which can be attributed to their relatively lower language proficiency. For example, some students complained that lecturers spoke very fast and use complicated words (Karahanna, Evaristo & Srite, 2005). Although educational stressors are experienced by all university students, their impact is more likely to be intensified due to the added stressors of language deficiency and cultural stressors among others (Heinrich, Rapee, Alden, Bogels, Hofmann, Oh & Sakano, 2006). Another study showed that international students who experienced educational stress had greater reactions to other stressors that they encountered when adjusting to the host culture. This might be compounded by work restrictions and higher tuition fees in the host country (Felfe, Yan & Six, 2008). Other practical stressors may include accommodation and transportation issues. International students who experienced discrimination and prejudice from their host culture were more likely to experience negative outcomes. Stereotypes could lead to performance decrements in achievement situations among academically committed students who were members of groups that were targeted with threats of intellectual inferiority. International students who go abroad for their studies might also become victims of prejudice and discrimination, and even harassment at an extreme (Fatima, Zamir, Ali & Fatima, 2018).

All the students were supposed to share acculturation despite of hailing from different cultural area and difference in language. There were some other problems that were faced by students apart from language and cultural difference upon their arrival at university premises, as they reach new surroundings, were academic demands, homesickness, loss of social support and status, decreased self-esteem, lack of study skills and lack of assertiveness (Fatima, Naz, Shabnam, Ali & Fatima, 2021). So as initially a new adjustment to environment and sense of isolation might result in psychological distress which might lead to deterioration of behavior (Fatima & Ali, 2019). Being a diverse culture in universities, people hold diverse opinions based on their personal beliefs and experiences. Varieties of experiences were held by students based on their culture, language, environment etc. Higher education students were being transformed by this diversity in culture globally. In simple words, accepting cultural diversity and enhancing students’ environment was quite significant to help students modifying their lives positively. In order to create a comfortable learning environment for different culturally background students, cultural diversity issues and strategies to form comprehensive learning environment should be addressed (Fatima & Ali, 2020). The other major factor to be considered while dealing with students of multi-cultural background was to apprehend their previous learning environment from the perspective of students which assisted them feel more homely and comfortable. To get accustomed to different cultural learning environment was defying and varied person to person (Fatima & Ali, 2017). According to cross-cultural psychologists, students got adjusted to new environment differently depending upon geographical distance and psychological backgrounds. Compared to South-Asian culture to the rest of world, students need to face some sought of tough and huge challenges due to being under hegemony of Confucius tradition, collectivism and linguistic structures (Dinev, Goo, Hu & Nam, 2009).

As there were many types of cultural difference that students dealt with. Out of these types, one most common and significant difference among students was assertiveness. Assertiveness is the tendency of a person what he/she thinks and feels. This factor was deemed to be a special avenue as one can pronounce his/her identification through it. The sense of assertiveness creates self-esteem in an individual and helps one mitigate his/her anxiety and help increase in internal control (Consedine, Strongman & Magai, 2003). In addition, the other major cultural difference that students deal with was collectivism. The reason why this being another major

factor is that student in university or higher educational institutes hail from different collectivist groups where inter-personal euphony was greatly appraised (Berry, 2003). A study showed that in the region of Asia, students hailing from different multi-cultural background were more submissive and less assertive (Akinkugbe, 2013). According to Akinkugbe (2013), “self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in his or her capacity to execute behaviors necessary to produce specific performance attainments. It reflects confidence in the ability to organize and control over one's own motivation, behavior, and social environment”. This element of self-efficacy in multi-cultural students had been found out to be most essential in regularizing their emotions. The strongest sense of self-efficacy among students was; the more emotional adjustment will be. It also assists students to cope with tough and challenging circumstances without feeling deluge and chaotic. Another study done by Koneru et al., (2007), “a discerned self-efficacy throws back an optimistic self-belief. This is quite particular to multi-cultural students. This optimistic self-belief in students will help them encounter troubles and tough task with great courage and bravery. This will also help them to facilitate goal-setting, endeavor investment, retrieval from mishaps and emotional flexibility”. Another major issue had been faced by students is their psychological change. When students tried to get accustomed to a non-native new environment, behavioral mutation occurred (Fatima & Ali, 2020). Mostly the psychological changes occur in students of higher educational institutes were positive but there could be sometimes negative psychological changes as well based on individual differences (Smaldino et al., 2019). As per some psychologists, severe homesickness is problematic for hostlers especially. This problem might lead to serious mental and physical health problems of students like depression and anxiety. In simple words, if students do not get their selves accustomed to host environment, the adjustment in university premises may be difficult for such students (Treven, Mulej & Lynn, 2008). Likewise, attitudinal change in student might cause problems for educators and instructors. Therefore, researchers were trying to investigate the degree of behavioral variations among university students regarding cultural impact on behavior.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Participants: This study was quantitative in nature. Descriptive design was used by survey method. 30,000 female students of international Islamic university Islamabad were constituted as the population. Department of Education has 1000 BS students and 1000 MS education female students. Students had Chinese and Pakistani nationality. 785 Students of education department of Islamic university was considered as sample of this study and this sample was taken through simple random sampling technique. 785 sample size was calculated through Epi Tool- a free web-based calculator. In this calculation, the margin of error (Precision) was 2.5%, Confidence intervals were 95%, the estimate prevalence from previous surveys is around 30% and population of students was 2000.

Research Instrument: Self-developed questionnaire was used in this study. It consisted of 35 items; this questionnaire was developed by keeping in view the objective of the study. Questionnaire was based on Berry model of acculturation (2013). Researchers used 25 questionnaires for measuring the validity and reliability before final administration of the questionnaire. The content validity of self-developed questionnaire was checked by the experts of social sciences who belong to International Islamic University and National University of Medical Sciences, Pakistan. They checked the phraseology and language of the instrument. Reliability of self-developed questionnaire was checked by Chronbach Alpha method. Through Exploratory factor analysis, construct validity was checked and then proper survey was conducted by researchers themselves.

Table 1

Reliability Scale

Sl.No	Variable	No. of Items	Chronbach Alpha
1	Students' Behavioral Variations across different culture	35	.864

Table 1 shows that all 35 items related to behavioral variations across different cultures are showing as reliable for final administration.

Data Analysis and its Interpretations

Data was organized into computer and analyzed by descriptive (Tabular and graphical representation of demographic factors and percentage responses of participants regarding questionnaires) and inferential statistics (t-test and ANOVA test) through SPSS.

Table 2

Demographic Factors

Factors	Frequency	Percent
Pakistani	380	48.4%
Chinese	404	51.6%
BS	417	53.1%
MS	368	46.9%

In this study 380 female students were Pakistani and 404 female students were Chinese. Similarly, 417 BS and 368 MS students were participated as the sample of this study.

Table 3

Means of Students' Behavioral Variations across different culture

<i>Sr.No</i>	<i>Dimensions of Behavioral Variations across different culture</i>	<i>Mean Value</i>
1	Stereotypical Factors	3.19
2	Migration Factors	3.32
3	Social Attitude and Behavior	3.26
4	Coping Strategy and Performance	3.29
5	Adaptation	3.14
	Students' Behavioral Variations across different culture	3.24

Majority of the students show neutral behavioral variations across different culture (M=3.24) because they were not fully confident in expressing their opinions about stereotypical factors (M=3.19), migration factors (M=3.32), Social attitude and behavior (M=3.26), coping strategy and performance (M=3.29) and adaptation (M= 3.14).

Table 4

Summary of Percentage Responses of Students towards Stereotypical factor

<i>N</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>SDA</i>	<i>DA</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1	Every student comes to university with the same chances for success	21.7%	23.4%	16.0%	29.1%	9.7%	2.81
2	Boys are naturally better athletes and leader than girls	6.9%	22.3%	29.1%	32.0%	9.7%	3.15
3	I respect the holidays and celebrations of religions and groups that are different than mine	1.7%	10.3%	37.1%	33.1%	17.7%	3.54
4	I have close friends of different races, ethnicities and genders	9.7%	14.3%	34.9%	25.7%	15.4%	3.22
5	I understand that society has favored one group over other	5.1%	23.4%	31.4%	20.6%	19.4%	3.25
6	Have you ever faced stereotypical behavior towards your culture from students of other cultures	9.1%	18.3%	34.9%	29.1%	8.6%	3.09
7	When interacting with men, I feel like they interpret all my behaviors in terms of the fact that I am a woman	5.1%	21.7%	34.9%	30.3%	8.0%	3.14
8	To what extent the institution helped you to continue your studies in this country	4.0%	15.4%	34.9%	37.1%	8.6%	3.30
9	Stereotypes about woman have not affected me personally	11.4%	10.9%	27.4%	36.0%	14.3%	3.30
10	There are groups or students who gossip about my cultural values and beliefs	6.3%	18.9%	36.0%	26.9%	12.0%	3.19

Table 4 shows the majority of the students agree that when every student comes to university with the same chances for success (29.1%, M=2.81); boys are naturally better athletes and leader than girls (32.0%, M=3.15); they respect the holidays and celebrations of religions and groups that are different than mine (37.1%, M=3.54); they have close friends of different races, ethnicities and genders (34.9%, M=3.22); they understand that society has favored one group over other (31.4%, M=3.25). Table also shows the majority of the students are neutral whenever they faced stereotypical behavior towards their culture from students of other cultures (34.9%, M=3.09); interacting with men, they felt like they interpreted all their behaviors in terms of the fact that they are women (34.9%, M=3.14); agree that the institution helped them to continue their studies in this country (37.1%, M=3.30); stereotypes about woman have not affected them personally (36.0%, M=3.30) and they show neutral behavior when the groups or students gossip about their cultural values and beliefs (36.0%, M=3.19).

Table 5

Summary of Percentage Responses of Students towards Migration Factor

<i>N</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>SDA</i>	<i>DA</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1	Migrants are always been treated as second class citizens	1.1%	24.0%	31.4%	34.9%	8.6%	3.25
2	Being rejected or stared at by others in the city merely because of my appearance and accent	1.7%	17.7%	30.3%	36.0%	14.3%	3.43

3	No matter what migrants do they can never change the fact that they are migrants	1.1%	22.9%	22.3%	34.3%	19.4%	3.48
4	Usually, migrants are unconfident about their own capabilities.	7.4%	21.1%	26.3%	24.6%	20.6%	3.29
5	Migrants have no options but to take the inferior jobs	8.0%	28.6%	25.1%	14.9%	23.4%	3.17

Table 5 shows the majority of the students are agree that migrants are always been treated as second class citizens (34.9%, M=3.25); being rejected or stared at by others in the city merely because of my appearance and accent (36.0%, M= 3.43); no matter what migrants do they can never change the fact that they are migrants (34.3%, M= 3.48); and neutral that usually migrants are unconfident about their own capabilities (26.3%,M=3.29) ; disagree that migrants have no options but to take the inferior jobs (28.6%, M=3.17).

Table 6

Summary of Percentage Responses of Students towards Social Attitude and Behavior

<i>N</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>SDA</i>	<i>DA</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1	Although people may speak different languages and dress in different ways, beneath the surface everyone is the same	8.0%	13.1%	18.9%	42.9%	17.1%	3.48
2	It is not usually necessary to know too much about someone's background in order to come to an understanding of who they are	2.3%	32.0%	29.1%	21.1%	15.4%	3.15
3	I think that first expressions are usually quite a good way of coming to a judgment about someone	17.1%	27.4%	11.4%	28.0%	16.0%	2.98
4	I think diversity makes it harder for people to work together	4.0%	21.7%	26.9%	35.4%	12.0%	3.29
5	I can rarely recognize when culture is having an impact on the effectiveness of my communication with people from different backgrounds	12.6%	12.6%	37.7%	29.1%	8.0%	3.07
6	During a conflict with peers, if the students engages in the problem behavior do peers leave the student alone	10.9%	17.1%	27.4%	37.7%	6.9%	3.12
7	Being on my own, taking responsibility for myself, has not been easy	0.6%	11.4%	37.1%	36.0%	14.9%	3.53
8	Does the social behavior occur during specific academic activities	5.7%	14.9%	15.4%	43.4%	20.6%	3.58
9	I find it easy to recognize when I am suffering from stress and anxiety	1.1%	14.9%	44.0%	22.9%	17.1%	3.40
10	It's ok to use stereotypical language as long as you are just kidding	15.4%	10.9%	36.6%	25.7%	11.4%	3.06

Table 6 shows the majority of the students are agree that the people may speak different languages and wear dress in different ways, beneath the surface everyone is the same (42.9%, M=3.48); disagree with knowing too much about someone's background in order to come to an understanding of who they are (32.0%, M=3.15); agree about the first expressions that are usually quite a good way of coming to a judgment about someone (28.0%, M=2.98); they thought that diversity makes it harder for people to work together (35.4%, M=3.29); neutral that they can rarely recognize when culture is having an impact on the effectiveness of my communication with people from different backgrounds (37.7%, M=3.07). Table also shows the majority of the students agree that in conflict with peers, if the students engage in the problem behavior leave them alone (37.7%, M=3.12); neutral that taking responsibility for themselves, has not been easy (37.1%, M=3.53); agree that the social behavior occur during specific academic activities (43.4%, M=3.58); neutral that they find it easy to recognize when they are suffering from stress and anxiety (44.0%, M=3.40); neutral that use stereotypical language as long as you are just kidding (36.6%, M=3.06).

Table 7
Summary of Percentage Responses of Students towards Coping Strategy and Performance

<i>N</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>SDA</i>	<i>DA</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1	I think that different perspectives can contribute greatly to good decision making	1.1%	13.7%	28.6%	30.9%	25.7%	3.66
2	Is academic performance having impact of the new culture you have learned	6.9%	16.6%	26.9%	32.6%	17.1%	3.36
3	What do you think that host culture accepted you or not	13.1%	8.6%	51.4%	26.3%	0.6%	2.92
4	Did u feel stress or anxiety while living in new culture or context	2.9%	15.4%	32.6%	44.0%	5.1%	3.33
5	Now Do you feel comfortable with students of host culture in classroom	7.4%	20.0%	30.9%	28.6%	13.1%	3.20

Table 7 shows the majority of the students are agree that different perspectives can contribute greatly to good decision making (30.9 %,M=3.66); academic performance has impact on the new culture through they have learned (32.6 %, M=3.36); neutral that the host culture accepted them or not (51.4 %, M=2.92); agree that they feel stress or anxiety while living in new culture or context (44.0 %, M=3.33); neutral that they feel comfortable with students of host culture in classroom (30.9 %, M=3.20).

Table 8
Summary of Percentage Responses of Students towards Adaptation

<i>N</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>SDA</i>	<i>DA</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1	I feel that I fit in well as part of the university environment	7.4%	9.7%	32.0%	41.7%	9.1%	3.35
2	Does the culture behavior occur to get your attention when you are working with other student	9.1%	11.4%	29.1%	40.6%	9.7%	3.30
3	I consciously reach out of students who are in minority group	4.0%	24.0%	40.0%	25.7%	6.3%	3.06
4	Does the cultural behavior/ behavioral changes occur in the presence of specific peers	7.4%	1.4%	42.3%	28.0%	10.9%	3.23
5	I am experiencing a lot of difficulty coping with the stresses imposed upon me	21.1%	18.9%	29.7%	20.0%	10.3%	2.79

Table 8 shows the majority of the students agree that they fit in well as part of the university environment (41.7%, M=3.35); the culture behavior occur to get their attention when they are working with other student (40.6%, M=3.30); neutral that they consciously reach out of students who are in minority group (40.0%, M3.06); neutral that the cultural behavior/behavioral changes occur in the presence of specific peers (42.3%, M=3.23); they experience a lot of difficulty coping with the stresses imposed upon them (29.7%, M=2.79).

Table 9
t-Test for Nationality regarding Students' Behavioral Variations across different culture

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Demographic factors</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t- value</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Students' Behavioral Variations across different culture	Pakistani	380	112.30 ± 15.59	173	-1.048	.296
	Chinese	404	114.87 ± 16.81			
	BS	417	114.70 ± 17.72	173	.938	.350
	MS	368	112.40 ± 14.38			

Table 9 table shows that the mean value of Pakistani students (M=112.3059) and mean value of Chinese students (M=114.8778). The difference in mean is not significant (p=.296). Similarly, the mean value of BS students (M=114.7097) and mean value of MS students (M=112.4024) show that this difference in mean is not significant (p=.350).

Discussion

Female students who were either belong to China and Pakistan had showed neutral opinion regarding behavioral variations across different culture because majority received respect and supportive attitude and behavior from teachers, peers and staff of the university. They didn't face any stereotypical behavior; however, they believed that they took time in migration, coping strategy and classroom performance and adaptation at university level due to cultural differences. These findings were quite similar with the work of Akinkuge (2013), Dinly et al.,

(2009) and Fatima (2019) who also found that individual may have different attitudes on the same topic, which makes them different from one another. There are also several determining factors that influence on them to develop a certain attitude, toward someone or something. Nevertheless, the outcome of both these is visible from the way they behave with concern to their attitudes. Similarly, Nationality and educational level had no effect on students' opinions about behavioral variations across different culture. This result was quite similar with the work of Fatima and Ali (2020) and Heinrich et al., (2006) who found that both Pakistani and Chinese students have close and supportive interaction with each-others. That is why they have showed neutral behaviors towards behavioral variations across different culture.

Conclusions

1. Female students were neutral about their behavioral variations across different culture like stereotypical, migration, social attitude and behavior, coping strategy and performance and adaptation at university level.
2. Nationality and level of Education had no significant effect over the students' opinions about behavioral variations across different culture at university level.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended to universities to organize the classes/courses or workshops to facilitate foreign students in order to learn language which would help them in communication. Secondly, students come from different cultural backgrounds having behavioral differences so teachers have to deal with all students equally and avoid all cultural biases which can affect student's performances.
2. This study may be conducted at all the universities of Pakistan as it was confined to only international Islamic university Islamabad.
3. Both qualitative and quantitative mode of research can be used that may give more accurate image of cultural behaviors.
4. This study was confined to females, so it can be conducted at males also.

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